

ANTIBIOTIC SELECTION BASED ON MICROBIOLOGY AND RESISTANCE PROFILES OF BILE AND BLOOD OF PATIENTS WITH ACUTE CHOLANGITIS

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ABSTRACT

Antimicrobial treatment with appropriate biliary drainage is considered the standard of care for acute cholangitis, but the optimal terms of antimicrobial therapy remains unknown. Six to 10 days of antimicrobial treatment are common for the treatment of acute cholangitis, but a recent retrospective cohort study suggested a shorter terms might be effective. A shorter duration of antimicrobial treatment can be beneficial in decreasing the length of hospital stay, improving patients' quality of life, decreasing adverse effects, and even contributing to a decrease in the occurrence of antimicrobial resistance.

Keywords: Acute cholangitis, microbiology, antibiotic, treatment.

Introduction. Acute cholangitis is the acute inflammation of the bile ducts, for which a prominent increase in the number of bacteria within the bile duct and a rise in bile duct pressure are crucial (Kiryama et al., 2018). The treatment for acute cholangitis mainly includes antimicrobial therapy and biliary decompression according to disease severity, and absence of treatment is associated with a high mortality risk [1]. The most up-to-date and widely used guideline on the subject is the 2018 Tokyo Guidelines (TG18) [2]. TG18 recommends four to seven days of antimicrobial therapy for patients with acute cholangitis once the source of infection has been controlled. However, the evidence level for this recommendation has been graded as low. Moreover, recent studies on acute cholangitis suggest that antimicrobial therapy for three days after successful ERCP is sufficient for treatment [3,4]. For mild or moderate acute cholecystitis, antimicrobial therapy for one day has also been reported to be sufficient after successful cholecystectomy [5,6]. In addition, several reports suggest that that even when antimicrobial therapy is ineffective, outcomes for patients with acute cholangitis are not worse if ERCP is successful.

The empiric antibiotics recommended for these organisms are β -lactam-based/ β -lactamase inhibitors, cephalosporins, carbapenems, and fluoroquinolones [7]. However, these choices are mostly based on previous studies of acute cholangitis, wherein bile specimens were sampled from the biliary tract using percutaneous transhepatic biliary drainage (PTBD) or endoscopic nasobiliary drainage (ENBD) and are potentially associated with microbial contamination from the catheter or by normal flora of the skin or gastrointestinal

tract [7]. The microbial and antibiotic resistance profiles of bile sampled from the gallbladder may provide more information in the context of acute cholangitis because most such infections are limited to the gallbladder, and sampling directly from the infection site increases the likelihood of identifying the true causative pathogen. Medical environments have changed over time, resulting in changes in bile microbiologic and antibiotic resistance patterns. Therefore, it is important to collect data that inform early appropriate antimicrobial therapy for patients with acute cholangitis [8].

Material and methods. This study was approved by Ethics Committee and was conducted in accordance with the ethical standards of the institution research committee and the Helsinki Declaration. Patients aged more than 18 years with the diagnosis of acute cholangitis by the Tokyo Guidelines criteria associated with common bile duct stone (CBDS) were enrolled from September 2019 to June 2023. ERCP for biliary drainage was performed on all patients within 72 hours after admission.

Results. The mean age of the patients was 62.3 ± 17.1 years, and the number of males (58.5%) was slightly higher than that of females (41.5%) in this study. Most patients had acute cholangitis with grade II severity (52.9%). Initial laboratory findings showed elevated white blood cell (WBC) counts ($13,584 \pm 5,485$ cells/ μ L) and total bilirubin (5.1 ± 1.9 mg/dL), aspartate aminotransferase (AST, 161.9 ± 256.8 IU/L), alanine aminotransferase (ALT, 138.5 ± 185.3 IU/L), and alkaline phosphatase (ALP, 231.3 ± 211.3 IU/L) levels (Table 1).

Table 1

Characteristics of patients.

	n=357
<i>Sex</i>	
Male	209 (58.5%)
Female	148 (41.5%)
<i>Grade of acute cholangitis</i>	
Mild I	147 (41.2%)
Moderate II	189 (52.9%)
Severe III	21 (5.9%)
PTBD	167
ERCP	190
<i>Laboratory findings</i>	
WBC count cells/ μ L	13,584 \pm 5.485
Total bilirubin (mg/dL)	5.1 \pm 1.9
AST (IU/L)	161.9 \pm 256.8
ALT (IU/L)	138.5 \pm 185.3
ALP (IU/L)	231.3 \pm 211.3

Overall, 493 bile cultures sampled within the study period were identified. From the remaining 357 bile duct cultures, a total of 892 microorganisms (bacteria or fungi) were isolated with polymicrobial growth detected in 71 % of cultures. The most frequent patho-

gens isolated were enterococci (33%) and enterobacteriales (31%), followed by *Candida spp.* (15.1%), streptococci (7.2%). *P. aeruginosa* represented 2.9% of bile culture isolates (Table 2). For the purpose of this study, only bacterial pathogens were considered for further evaluation.

Table 2

Frequency of microorganisms isolated in bile and blood

	Bile N=892	Blood N=94
Enterococcus spp.	33 %	19 %
Enterobacteriales	31%	59 %
E.coli	15.4 %	35.4 %
Klebsiella spp.	9.1 %	16 %
Enterobacter spp.	3.1 %	6 %
Citrobacter spp.	2.4 %	3.1 %
Other enterobacteriales	3.2 %	3.3 %
Candida spp.	15.1%	2.9 %
Streptococcus spp.	7.2 %	1 %
Coagulase-negative staphylococci	3.1 %	3.3 %
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	2.9 %	8.1 %
Other	6 %	6 %

We identified 176 blood cultures collected within 48 h of the respective bile samples. Seventy five of these had turned positive. Polymicrobial growth was less frequent in blood than in bile cultures. Complete or partial pathogen concordance with corresponding bile cultures was present in 57%. While in bile cultures enterobacteriales and enterococci were isolated with similar frequencies (approximately 25%), enterobacteriales

comprised the majority of isolates in blood cultures (59% compared to 19% enterococci).

With the exception of carbapenems, a high level of resistance against all classes of antibiotics tested was found in enterobacteriales isolated from bile or blood. Also, at least one third of enterococci isolated from bile and blood were resistant to ampicillin (Table 3).

Table 3

Antibiotic treatment

	Frequency	n
Mono therapy	56.6	202
Combinational therapy	43.4	155
<i>Prescribed antibiotic substances</i>		
Cephalosporine 2 nd gen	34.5%	123
Cephalosporine 3 rd gen	31%	111
Piperazillin/tazobactam	21 %	75
Carbapenem	17.7 %	63
Fluorochinolon	17 %	61
Ampicillin/sulbactam	12.4 %	44
Metronidazole	14.3 %	51

Discussion. Polymicrobial infections have been frequently reported in previous studies of biliary disease, and antibiotic regimens consisting of two or more agents are often recommended. However, mono-microbial growth was predominant in this study, indicating that antibiotic selection should be different for patients with acute cholecystitis compared with those with other biliary tract infections [9].

Bile has antimicrobial properties, which results in the sterility of the biliary tract under non-pathogenic conditions. However, gram-negative microorganisms, commonly found in the intestinal tract, such as Enterobacteriales were frequently isolated from patients with biliary infection. Owing to the development of defense mechanisms, Enterobacteriales, especially *Escherichia*, became more resistant to bile than gram-positive microorganisms, thus becoming less sensitive to the deleterious effects of bile so that they frequently colonized the gallbladder and became an important reservoir for biliary infections [10].

Empirical therapy of cholangitis represents an educated guess based on spectrum and likelihood of causative pathogens and their expected antimicrobial susceptibility. Accordingly, the current Tokyo guideline recommends third generation cephalosporines, piperacillin/tazobactam or carbapenems for empirical treatment the choice of which should be guided by local susceptibility data and the severity of the infection. For severe cases and hospital-acquired infections anti-pseudomonal agents and coverage of enterococci are recommended. Because optimal empirical treatment may vary greatly between different institutions, a multidisciplinary approach is suggested [12]

Conclusion. In conclusion, the incidence of frequently isolated microorganisms and their antibiotic resistance profiles changed over time. The frequency of infections caused by gram-positive microorganisms, including enterococci, significantly declined during the period under study, whereas infections caused by gram-negative microorganisms, including Enterobacteriales, especially *E. coli*, showed a significant increasing trend. Only the combined analysis of microbiological and patient data revealed piperacillin/tazobactam as an excellent choice for empiric therapy of patients with acute cholangitis.

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